

Smartphone Authentication with Lightweight Deep Learning

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Abstract—Over the past decade, machine learning methods have found their way into a large variety of computer security applications, including accurate spam detection, scalable discovery of new malware families, identifying malware download events in vast amounts of web traffic, detecting software exploits, blocking phishing web pages, and preventing fraudulent financial transactions, just to name a few. At the same time, machine learning methods themselves have evolved. In particular, Deep Learning methods have recently demonstrated great improvements over more “traditional” learning approaches on a number of important tasks, including image and audio classification, natural language processing, machine translation, etc. Deep learning has faced an exponential growth over the last decade. Today, it has found use in a wide range of applications, security being one of those. In this project we try to exploit deep learning methodologies to facilitate user authentication on smartphones. Smartphone authentication has explored a variety of domains like iris recognition (latest Samsung Galaxy S8), face recognition (iPhoneX), fingerprints (traditional iPhones), PINs and pattern recognitions (traditional smartphones). In this project, we try to develop a lightweight authentication scheme based on sensor data which continually authenticates the user at regular intervals of time, thus providing greater security.

1. Introduction

Deep learning has emerged as one of the leading technologies of AI over the past decade [Goodfellow et al.(2016)Goodfellow, Bengio, and Courville], [Learning(2020)], [LeCun et al.(2015)LeCun, Bengio, and Hinton] but it still falls prey to one big disadvantage - it is really data hungry and consumes a lot of resources to output the best results [Saha et al.(2022a)], [Patel et al.(2016)Patel, Chellappa, Chandra, and Barbello]. Here, we try to tackle these problems through various heuristics and algorithms [Abuhamad et al.(2020)Abuhamad, Abuhmed, Mohaisen, and Nyang]. Reducing the model size and time of computation without sacrificing its performance can make deep learning a very important tool on smartphones [Saha et al.(2021)Saha, Aaraj, Ajarapu, and Jha], [Brown et al.(2021)Brown, Saha, and Jha]. We believe that security is just the starting point to embed deep learning primitives into smartphones [Schwag and Saha(2016)]. Once the deep learning primitives are engineered into the resource constrained embedded devices like smartphones [Mekruk-

savanich and Jitpattanukul(2021)], we enter into a world of new possibilities [Saha et al.(2022b)Saha, Aaraj, and Jha].

In this project, we have the following objectives:

- Tuning the hyperparameters to get the best results with minimum resources [Toal et al.(2008)Toal, Bressloff, and Keane]
- Reducing the model size to make it possible to operate on a smartphone [Volaka et al.(2019)Volaka, Alptekin, Basar, Isbilen, and Incel]
- Reducing the time of computation to make it feasible for real-world user authentication
- Reducing the input data required for correct prediction.

2. Methodology

We use a MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron) as our deep learning model. The reason for choosing this is that this is the simplest and most lightweight model available. Hence, we believe that embedding this into a smartphone will be the first step in integrating other complex models like convolutional neural networks (CNN), recurrent neural networks (RNN), and long short-term memory (LSTM) cells into smartphones [Centeno et al.(2017)Centeno, van Moorsel, and Castruccio].

2.1. Factors influencing the performance of MLP

The performance of neural networks is highly dependent on the initialization of their hyperparameters [Schratz et al.(2019)Schratz, Muenchow, Iturrity, Richter, and Brenning]. Hyperparameters are parameters that control the learning process and they are unaltered by the training process. We will address efficient tuning of hyperparameters for best performance in subsequent sections. Here, we want to address the factors other than hyperparameters that influence the performance of a neural network. Some of these parameters are:

- Splitting of Training/Development Sets determines the training accuracy. It also has some influence on the Testing accuracy as the weights of the DNN are affected by the data of the Training dataset.
- Bias/Variance of the classifier
- Regularization (choosing parameter lambda)
- Normalizing the inputs to reduce the time of gradient descent by orders of magnitude (already provided in sample code)

- Vanishing/Exploding gradients — If the gradients are greater than 1 then they tend to be very large with increasing layers and they tend to zero when the initial gradients are less than 1. That is why performing numerical approximation of gradients and gradient checking methods are preferable.

2.1.1. Measures taken to improve performance of MLP.

In this section, we discuss the steps we have implemented to boost the performance of our MLP model.

- Implementing Mini-batch gradient descent — If batch size = 1, it is synonymous to stochastic gradient descent which doesn't make use of vectorization and if batch size = 'no. of examples in training set' then every iteration takes too long.
- Bias correction using exponentially weighted averages
- Adam optimization algorithm is used which uses gradient descent with momentum and bias correction with exponentially weighted averages to predict faster and better.
- Splitting of training/development Sets determines the training accuracy. It also has some influence on the testing accuracy as the weights of the deep neural networks (DNNs) are affected by the data of the training dataset.
- Learning rate decay.

Most importantly, we have performed a rigorous fine tuning of the hyperparameters. The factors mentioned above are extra measures taken to improve performance.

2.2. Hyperparameter Tuning Strategy

The following hyperparameters are to be fine tuned to maximize the performance of the model. They are arranged in decreasing order of importance. So, we start tuning the hyperparameters in the same order.

- Learning Rate (Priority 1)
- Activation function (Priority 1)
- Number of layers (Priority 2)
- Number of hidden units in every layer (Priority 2)
- Mini-batch size (Priority 3)
- Standard deviation of normal distribution in initialization (Priority 3)
- Number of epochs (Priority 4)

We achieved an accuracy of 98.86% with the initial parameters. We mention the initial parameters below:

- Number of layers (of the MLP network architecture) : 3 hidden layers (including the output layer)
- Number of hidden nodes in each layer: Layer 1: 20, Layer 2: 10, Layer 3: 6
- Learning rate (typically within $1e-6$ to 1.0) : $1e-3$
- Number of training epochs : 10
- Batch size used in training phase:40
- Standard deviation of the normal distribution in initialization : 0.1

TABLE 1: Activation function vs. accuracy

Activation Function	Accuracy (%)
relu	41.9298 (lowest)
relu6	94.677 (highest)
sigmoid	93.653
tanh	94.031
softsign	93.036
softplus	42.000

Now, we tune these parameters to make the model lightweight and boost performance at the same time. Next, we describe the fine-tuning process of every hyperparameter in detail.

2.2.1. Learning rate. The learning rate is preferred to be in the order of magnitude of $1e-3$ [Schaul et al.(2013)Schaul, Zhang, and LeCun]. However, we take multiple random values of learning rate and conduct experiments. The results are shown in the graph below. It is seen that the model performs best when the learning rate is in the range of $1e-3$ to $1e-2$. Based on our experiments, we choose the learning rate to be 0.002. We demonstrate our experimental results of accuracy vs. learning rates in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Accuracy vs learning rate graph

2.2.2. Activation function. The default activation function used for the hidden layers is the sigmoid function. We try other activation functions like the ReLU and tanh functions and plot a graph. To observe a clear impact of the activation function on accuracy, we set the learning rate = 1 (which is a bad choice but helps us to visualize the impact of activation functions on the accuracy of the MLP). We demonstrate the performance of various activation functions in Table 1.

2.2.3. Number of layers. The default number of layers was 3. Generally, a deep learning model has 2-4 hidden layers. Since, we get an accuracy of $>99\%$ with 3 layers, we decrease the number of layers to 2 and carry out our experiments. We observe that the accuracy changes negligibly and is maintained at $>99\%$. This is because of carefully choosing the learning rate. So, we fix the number of layers to 2.

2.2.4. Number of hidden units in each layer. The final layer has fixed number of hidden units and that is equal

to the number of different class labels (6 in our case). The accuracy vs number of units in hidden layer 1 is plotted in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Accuracy vs learning rate graph

2.2.5. Mini-batch size. Due to the problem of alignment of the virtual processors (VP) onto the physical processors (PP) of the GPU, it is convenient to keep the mini-batch size to be a power of 2. The explanation is as follows. Since the number of PP is often a power of 2, using a number of VP different from a power of 2 leads to poor performance. One can see the mapping of the VP onto the PP as a pile of slices of size the number of PP.

Say there are 16 PP. One can map 16 VP on them: 1 VP is mapped onto 1 PP. One can map 32 VP on them : 2 slices of 16 VP, 1 PP will be responsible for 2 VP, etc. During execution, each PP will execute the job of the 1st VP he is responsible for, then the job of the 2nd VP etc. If you use 17 VP, each PP will execute the job of their 1st PP, then 1 PP will execute the job of the 17th and the other ones will do nothing. This is due to the SIMD paradigm (called vector in the 70s) used by GPUs. This is often called Data Parallelism : all the PP do the same thing at the same time but on different data. More precisely, in the example with 17 VP, once the job of the 1st slice done (by all the PPs doing the job of their 1st VP), all the PP will do the same job (2nd VP), but only one has some data to work on.

2.2.6. Standard deviation of normal distribution in initialization. The default value of this was 0.1 . It is a good practice to set the std dev of the initial weights to squareroot(2/n) for Relu activation functions, where n is the number of units in the input layer. We set the std dev of the initial weights of layer 1 to sqrt(2/n) and the std dev of the second layer to 0.1 as the second layer doesn't use ReLu.

2.2.7. Number of epochs. A graph is plotted to determine the number of epochs to get optimum performance in terms of accuracy and computation time. The number of epochs is set to be 7 (accuracy 99.5%). We demonstrate the accuracy change over number of epochs in Fig. 3.

2.2.8. Learning Rate Decay. We implemented learning rate decay but not much changes in accuracy were observed. This

Figure 3: Accuracy over epochs

TABLE 2: Optimized parameters of MLP

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	0.002
Number of hidden layers	2
Number of hidden units	Layer 1: 12; Layer 2: 6
Mini-batch size	32
Standard deviation of initial weights	sqrt(1/3)
Epochs	7
Validation accuracy	99.51%
Train time	3.41 s
Inference time	0.21 s
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-5350U 1.80GHz
	8 GB 1600 MHz DDR3
	Intel HD Graphics 6000 1536 MB
Size of trained model	44.47 kB

is because a very high accuracy has already been achieved. However, we report the various learning rate decay models we used:

- Exponential Decay $r = 0.95^{epochs} \times alpha$
- $r = (k/sqrt(epochs)) \times alpha$
- staircase function of learning rate vs epochs

3. Results

We demonstrate the final hyperparameters in Table 2.

Using this model, the number of misclassifications for every user are given in Fig. 4. Fig. 4 demonstrates that user 1 is most likely to be misclassified and user 8 is least likely to be misclassified.

Reducing the sensors: This requires choosing the best features from the dataset. We use tree-based methods to calculate feature importances which are in turn used to discard irrelevant features. We use the ExtraTrees Classifier module from sklearn.ensemble library to assign importance values to the feature based on different metrics like variance, Fisher score, correlation coefficients, etc. This leads to the elimination of 10 features without any loss in accuracy. Surprisingly, nearly the same accuracy of 99.5% was reached in 4 epochs instead of 7.

As observed from Fig. 5, 8 features have maximum influence. The others are considered irrelevant. The features being retained, with an importance value $> 5\%$, are:

Figure 4: Accuracy vs learning rate graph

- rotation x
- rotation y
- rotation z
- magnetometer x
- magnetometer y
- magnetometer z
- pressure
- light
- proximity

Hence, only 5 sensors are being used. They are the rotation sensor, magnetometer, barometer, light sensor and proximity sensor.

Figure 5: Importance of various features during prediction

This causes a negligible degradation in accuracy. The accuracy declines by 0.12%. On the other hand, the prediction time decreases drastically, being almost 50% of the previous value. The inference time decreases due to the decrease in the number of epochs. So, this is a good trade-off between accuracy and computation time as one of them decreases drastically while the other declines negligibly. We show these results in Table 3.

Reducing the time of computation and size of MLP: Now that our MLP model is fully working with optimized accuracy, we need to make some trade-offs so that the computation time and model size are reduced. This will enable it to be integrated on a smartphone. Since, the prediction

TABLE 3: Optimized parameters for a reduced sensors MLP model

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	0.002
Number of hidden layers	2
Number of hidden units	Layer 1: 12; Layer 2: 6
Mini-batch size	32
Standard deviation of initial weights	sqrt(1/3)
Epochs	4
Validation accuracy	99.38%
Train time	1.87 s
Inference time	0.16 s
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-5350U 1.80GHz 8 GB 1600 MHz DDR3 Intel HD Graphics 6000 1536 MB
Size of trained model	42.47 kB

is to be performed on chunks of 50 continuous samples of data from the same user we can target an accuracy around 90% instead of going as high as 99%. Then we can use a majority voting to predict the user. To reduce the inference time, we reduce the number of epochs to just 1 as it is enough to give an accuracy >90%. High speed is highly desirable as higher the speed is, higher will be the user convenience. We try to reduce the size of the model by reducing the number of hidden units in hidden layer 1. Then we can also use this scheme for continuous authentication of the user at regular intervals of time without consuming a lot of battery power. This will make it lightweight as well as fast. The size of our model is as small as 41.47 KB while the accuracy is 96.87%. The training time is 0.22s while the inference time has also improved to 0.2877s. The model size being so small, it is a very lucrative option for being implemented on a smartphone. Most of the apps have sizes in the range of MBs. However, this can be modeled into app having a size in KBs. We guess that since this model is so lightweight and accurate at the same time, it is not only feasible to be used on a smartphone but also a very good alternative to current authentication schemes as it can provide continuous authentication users without bothering them frequently for passwords or biometrics. We demonstrate our final optimized parameters for the MLP model with reduced sensors in Table 4.

TABLE 4: Final optimized parameters for a reduced sensors MLP model

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	0.002
Number of hidden layers	2
Number of hidden units	Layer 1: 7; Layer 2: 6
Mini-batch size	32
Standard deviation of initial weights	sqrt(1/3)
Epochs	1
Validation accuracy	96.87%
Train time	0.29 s
Inference time	0.22 s
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-5350U 1.80GHz 8 GB 1600 MHz DDR3 Intel HD Graphics 6000 1536 MB
Size of trained model	41.47 kB

4. Conclusion

In this project, we build a deep learning model using a Multi Layer Perceptron that uses smartphone sensor data to identify various users [Hossain et al.(2022)Hossain, Islam, and Akhtar]. Sensor data can be accessed by any app without explicit permissions from the user [Saha et al.(2022c)Saha, Aaraj, and Jha]. This model can be used for continuous user authentication [Lee and Lee(2017)]. This is a very helpful tool as it makes the device much more secure and the smartphone will get locked immediately when some other user tries to access it, since user authentication takes places continuously [Song et al.(2016)Song, Wang, Ren, and Xu].

We fine-tuned the hyperparameters and made many modifications so that it can effectively run on a smartphone. The final model takes about a third of memory required by the original model. It also works orders of magnitude faster than the initial model.

This project gave us a deep insight into how deep learning paradigms can be used in security applications [Buriro et al.(2016)Buriro, Crispo, Delfrari, and Wrona]. Moreover, it gave us a deep understanding about how deep learning works in practical scenarios. We learned the detailed impacts of each hyperparameter on the performance of the model and how to iterate and fine-tune them. We also got a introduced to various activation functions, softmax function and optimization algorithms (Adam Optimizer).

This project can be considered as a great introduction of utilizing deep learning in the domain of security.

References

- [Goodfellow et al.(2016)Goodfellow, Bengio, and Courville] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep learning*. MIT press, 2016.
- [Learning(2020)] D. Learning, “Deep learning,” *High-dimensional fuzzy clustering*, 2020.
- [LeCun et al.(2015)LeCun, Bengio, and Hinton] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, “Deep learning,” *nature*, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp. 436–444, 2015.
- [Saha et al.(2022a)] T. Saha *et al.*, “Machine learning-based efficient and generalizable cybersecurity frameworks,” 2022.
- [Patel et al.(2016)Patel, Chellappa, Chandra, and Barbelo] V. M. Patel, R. Chellappa, D. Chandra, and B. Barbelo, “Continuous user authentication on mobile devices: Recent progress and remaining challenges,” *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 49–61, 2016.
- [Abuhamad et al.(2020)Abuhamad, Abuhmed, Mohaisen, and Nyang] M. Abuhamad, T. Abuhmed, D. Mohaisen, and D. Nyang, “Autosen: Deep-learning-based implicit continuous authentication using smartphone sensors,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 5008–5020, 2020.
- [Saha et al.(2021)Saha, Aaraj, Ajarapu, and Jha] T. Saha, N. Aaraj, N. Ajarapu, and N. K. Jha, “Sharks: Smart hacking approaches for risk scanning in internet-of-things and cyber-physical systems based on machine learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 870–885, 2021.
- [Brown et al.(2021)Brown, Saha, and Jha] J. Brown, T. Saha, and N. K. Jha, “Gravitas: Graphical reticulated attack vectors for internet-of-things aggregate security,” *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1331–1348, 2021.
- [Schwag and Saha(2016)] V. Schwag and T. Saha, “Tv-puf: a fast lightweight analog physical unclonable function,” in *2016 IEEE International Symposium on Nanoelectronic and Information Systems (iNIS)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 182–186.
- [Mekruksavanich and Jitpattanakul(2021)] S. Mekruksavanich and A. Jitpattanakul, “Deep learning approaches for continuous authentication based on activity patterns using mobile sensing,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 22, p. 7519, 2021.
- [Saha et al.(2022b)Saha, Aaraj, and Jha] T. Saha, N. Aaraj, and N. K. Jha, “Machine learning assisted security analysis of 5g-network-connected systems,” *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2006–2024, 2022.
- [Toal et al.(2008)Toal, Bressloff, and Keane] D. J. Toal, N. W. Bressloff, and A. J. Keane, “Kriging hyperparameter tuning strategies,” *AIAA journal*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 1240–1252, 2008.
- [Volaka et al.(2019)Volaka, Alptekin, Basar, Isbilen, and Incel] H. C. Volaka, G. Alptekin, O. E. Basar, M. Isbilen, and O. D. Incel, “Towards continuous authentication on mobile phones using deep learning models,” *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 155, pp. 177–184, 2019.
- [Centeno et al.(2017)Centeno, van Moorsel, and Castruccio] M. P. Centeno, A. van Moorsel, and S. Castruccio, “Smartphone continuous authentication using deep learning autoencoders,” in *2017 15th annual conference on privacy, security and trust (pst)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 147–1478.
- [Schratz et al.(2019)Schratz, Muenchow, Iturrityxa, Richter, and Brenning] P. Schratz, J. Muenchow, E. Iturrityxa, J. Richter, and A. Brenning, “Hyperparameter tuning and performance assessment of statistical and machine-learning algorithms using spatial data,” *Ecological Modelling*, vol. 406, pp. 109–120, 2019.
- [Schaul et al.(2013)Schaul, Zhang, and LeCun] T. Schaul, S. Zhang, and Y. LeCun, “No more pesky learning rates,” in *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 2013, pp. 343–351.
- [Hossain et al.(2022)Hossain, Islam, and Akhtar] M. S. Hossain, M. T. Islam, and Z. Akhtar, “Incorporating deep learning into capacitive images for smartphone user authentication,” *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, vol. 69, p. 103290, 2022.
- [Saha et al.(2022c)Saha, Aaraj, and Jha] T. Saha, N. Aaraj, and N. K. Jha, “System and method for security in internet-of-things and cyber-physical systems based on machine learning,” Jun. 23 2022, uS Patent App. 17/603,453.
- [Lee and Lee(2017)] W.-H. Lee and R. B. Lee, “Implicit smartphone user authentication with sensors and contextual machine learning,” in *2017 47th Annual IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks (DSN)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 297–308.
- [Song et al.(2016)Song, Wang, Ren, and Xu] C. Song, A. Wang, K. Ren, and W. Xu, “Eyeveri: A secure and usable approach for smartphone user authentication,” in *IEEE INFOCOM 2016-The 35th Annual IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–9.
- [Buriro et al.(2016)Buriro, Crispo, Delfrari, and Wrona] A. Buriro, B. Crispo, F. Delfrari, and K. Wrona, “Hold and sign: A novel behavioral biometrics for smartphone user authentication,” in *2016 IEEE security and privacy workshops (SPW)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 276–285.